

Project information

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LEAPS-INNOV 1st Annual Meeting Group picture

LEAPS-INNOV 1st Annual Meeting Description

The LEAPS-INNOV 1st Annual Meeting took place as a face-to-face meeting in a hybrid format 3-5 May 2022, in Casa Convalescencia (UAB), Barcelona, Spain.

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The aim of the Annual Meeting was to bring together the LEAPS-INNOV project community to let the work packages (WPs) meet in person for the first time and discuss achieved and planned work, for an exchange across all WPs, for discussing the project's relevant current issues and discuss and engage with the LEAPS-INNOV Innovation Advisory Board. Due to the pandemic, the LEAPS-INNOV kick-off meeting was only possible as pure digital meeting and therefore, the *in-person* meeting was very much welcomed and hybrid options were offered whenever needed.

160 registered LEAPS-INNOV members participated the Annual Meeting, 45 out of the 160 in remote mode (see *Participants List*). The participants included representatives from all project beneficiaries, WP leaders and their members, members of the Governing Board and Innovation Advisory Board, and special guests, e.g. the project coordinators of the INFRA-INNOV pilots Aida-Innova and I.FAST - overall a broad, diverse and international audience.

The LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meeting 2022 was opened by a Welcome from Caterina Biscari, LEAPS Vice Chair and ALBA CELLS director, followed by Elke Plönjes, the LEAPS-INNOV Scientific Coordinator. Two half days were dedicated to individual WP sessions allowing detailed discussions and brainstorming for the WPs in a fruitful atmosphere and with a dinner for the WPs only for socialising within the individual WPs. WP leaders reported from very constructive WP meetings during the closing Executive Board meeting. Furthermore, the transversal WPs WP8 and WP9 participated during a specific time slot to the other technical WPs to discuss specific issues on industry and co-creation.

The Plenary Session was opened by a cordial Welcome and introductory talk by the Scientific Coordinator Elke Plönjes (DESY). She highlighted the LEAPS-INNOV pilot project focussing on the implementation of new strategies and activities for partnership between industry and the photon science community, in particular the European synchrotron radiation light sources and free electron lasers with their ten thousand of users, including high-impact industrial applications. Thus, the pilot project will contribute to solving key technological challenges for the next generation of photon sources, the up-coming diffraction-limited storage rings and the still novel X-ray FELs, over 50 facilities in Europe and worldwide. A brief introduction to the project and its context as well as an update concerning the project governance, encompassing the project bodies with their respective composition and roles, was given.

The project's embedding consortium LEAPS (League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources) with its current and future main activities and strategy was presented by Ana Valcarel-Orti (SOLEIL), LEAPS Coordination Board Vice Chair. In the context of open innovation, industry involvement was centrally included in the program, reflected as specific talks (e.g. by the CEO of a LEAPS-INNOV beneficiary SME, a talk from the facility 'perspective, and a talk on a new digital innovation mall model functioning as an expert networking platform with industry) and a panel discussion with the Innovation Advisory Board. Two young scientists (post-docs) were invited to present their plans and first result of their work in the project and the LEAPS-INNOV twin pilot project coordinators of AIDA-INNOVA and I.FAST presented their work in progress (vice versa, the LEAPS-INNOV coordinator did during their Annual Meetings). The Innovation Advisory Board (IAB) discussed how to engage best and most useful with advice to the project and voted a chair and vice chair during its constitutive meeting in a closed session. The Governing Board approved the IAB and its chairs and was informed about the progress and status.

The WP leaders presented the project's progress after the first year, with detailed insight into the progress of each work package, featuring achievements and highlights as well as the relevant next

actions and including estimated delays in deliverables and milestones as well as a showcase of selected achievements from both technical and non-technical work packages. Furthermore, a brief insight into financial regulations and reporting was given. WP leaders met to wrap up during a short Executive Board meeting and it was common agreement that despite of the start has taken place during the pandemic, the project is functioning well and has achieved successes thanks to the hard work and the enthusiastic collaborative spirit of the LEAPS-INNOV community - work packages managers, task leaders and all project participants. All presentation slides can be found on the project shared folder on the DESY Cloud, available to all project members. The agenda granted plenty of opportunities for formal as well as informal exchange. A survey has been sent to the participants shortly after the Annual Meeting to capture the collective mood and suggestions to improve. Altogether, the mixture of informative and insightful presentations, exchange formats such as Q&As as well as fruitful networking opportunities during the breaks and dinners and discussions contributed to an engaging, lively and successful hybrid event.

LEAPS-INNOV 1st Annual Meeting Agenda

LEAPS-INNOV: Annual Meeting Agenda 03 – 05 May, 2022 Barcelona (Casa Convalescencia)

Tuesday May 3, 2022

14:00h [Coffee Networking](#)

15:00h Welcome by LEAPS Vice Chair Caterina Biscari

15:10 – 18:30h WP Session 1 (parallel WP meetings)

18:30h [End of Day 1](#)

20:00h [WP dinners \(at own cost\)](#)

Wednesday May 4, 2022

9:00 - 13:00h WP Session 2 (parallel WP meetings)

9:00 – 10:30 WP2 – WP7: parallel meetings with visitors of WP8 & WP9

10:30 [Coffee Break](#)

11:00 – 13:00 WP2 – WP9 parallel meetings

13:00 [Networking Lunch](#)

LEAPS-INNOV PLENARY MEETING

14:00 – 15:30h Plenary Session 1

- 14:00 Introduction by the Coordinator, Elke Plönjes (20')
- 14:20 LEAPS – strategy & priorities 2022, key activities, Ana Valcarel-Orti (10')

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- 14:30 Qualification of a company by a facility, example: DESY, Hans Weise (20`)
- 14:50 Panel Discussion with IAB members (40`)

15:30 - 16:15h [Networking Coffee Break](#)

16:15 – 17:45h Plenary Session 2

- 16:15 How to build a spin-off/start-up, Florian Döring (20`)
- 16:35 Fabrication of X-Ray Gratings by Grey-Tone Electron-Beam Lithography and Thermal Oxidation of Silicon, Young Scientist talk, Samadi Nazanin (15`)
- 16:50 High-temperature superconducting undulator prototype, Young Scientist talk, Xiaoyang Liang (15`)
- 17:05 Innovation pilot projects Aida-INNOVA, Paolo Giacomelli & I.FAST, Maurizio Vretenar (20`)
- 17: 25 HR4 Innovation Mall, Antonio Bonucci (20`)

18:00 – 19:00h **IAB Meeting (hybrid), closed session** (IAB members, Coordinator & WP8 rep.)

19:00h [End of Day 2](#)

20:15h [Joint Dinner \(Casa Convalescencia, venue\)](#)

Thursday May 5, 2022

9:00h GB meeting (closed session, hybrid)

10:00h Report from WPs

12:00h Closing remarks, Coordinator Next steps

12:30h [End of Day 3 \(not EB\)](#)

12:30h EB meeting (Brainstorming, follow up actions)

13:15 [End of Day 3 for all](#)

LEAPS-INNOV 1st Annual Meeting Participant List

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Name	Affiliation	Work package	1 dig
Yves-Marie ABIVEN	synchrotron SOLEIL	WP5	0
Clara Albert	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP2; WP3;WP4;WP6; WP7	1
Simon Alcock	Diamond Light Source, UK	WP3; WP4	0
Matteo Amati	Elettra - Sincrotrone Trieste S.C.p.A.	WP5	0
Peter Anastasi	Silson Ltd	WP8	0
Jose Avila Abellan	CELLS - ALBA Synchrotron	WP5	0
Antonella Balerna	INFN-LNF	WP2	1
Ray Barrett	ESRF	WP3; WP4	0
Axel Bernhard	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	WP6	1
Martin Beye	FS-FLASH (FLASH)	WP4	1
Cecilia Blasetti	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste	WP9	1
Mirko Boin	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin	WP8	1
Antonio Bonucci	European XFEL	WP6; WP8	0
Patrice Bras	ESRF	WP3	1
Barbara Calisto	ALBA synchrotron	WP9	0
Marco Calvi	PSI	WP6	0
Sara Casalbuoni	European XFEL	WP6	1
Joan Casas	ALBA Synchrotron	WP5	0
Michele Cascella	MAX IV	WP2	0
Gamil CASSAM-CHENAI	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP7	0
Yngve Cerenius	MAX IV	WP3	0
Mariangela Cestelli Guidi	INFN - Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati	WP8	0
Sudeep Chatterji	Diamond Light Source Ltd	WP2	1
Piotr Ciochoń	SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre	WP8	1
Cédric COHEN	ESRF	WP2	0
Carles Colldelram Peroliu	CELLS-ALBA	WP2; WP3; WP5	0
Marie Emmanuelle Couprie		WP6	0
Agnieszka Cudek	SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre	WP8	1
Guifré Cuní	ALBA Synchrotron	WP5	0
Christian David	Paul Scherrer Institut	WP4	0
Philippe DEBLAY	SOLEIL	WP8	1
Thomas Dehaeze	ESRF	WP5	1
Angela den Hollander	Radboud University, FELIX	WP8; WP9	0

Graham Dennis	Diamond Light Source	WP2	0
Simone Di Mitri	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste	WP6	0
Florian Döring	XRnanotech	WP4	0
Guillaume Dovillaire	Imagine Optic	WP3; WP8	0
Ludovic DUCOTTE	ESRF	WP5	1
Sebastien Ducourtieux	Synchrotron Soleil	WP5	0
Jamal El Mansouri	SOLEIL	WP8	1
Christer Engblom	Synchrotron Soleil	WP5	0
Pablo Fajardo	ESRF	WP2	0
Emmanuel FARHI	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP7	0
Vanesa Faro	CELLS	WP8	0
Vincent Favre-Nicolin	ESRF-The European Synchrotron	WP7	0
Analía Fernández Herrero	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin	WP4	0
Uwe Flechsig	PSI	WP3; WP4	0
Jens Flügge	PTB	WP5	1
Rachel Freeman	Diamond Light Source	WP8	0
Juan Luis Frieiro Castro	CELLS-ALBA	WP2; WP3; WP5	0
Peter Gaal	TXproducts UG (haftungsbeschränkt)	WP5	0
Brigitte Gagey	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP7	1
Felicita Gernhardt	HZDR	WP7	0
Luca Giannessi	INFN	WP6	0
Heinz Graafsma	FS-DS (Detektorsysteme)	WP2; WP7 D	0
Rita Graceffa	European XFEL	WP6; WP8; WP9	1
Andreas Grau	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	WP6	0
Francesco Guzzi		WP7	0
Michael Hagelstein	Karlsruher Institut für Technologie	WP8	0
Sameea Hassim	SOLEIL	WP9	0
Julia Hauk	EUP (EU-Projekt)	WP1	0
Elena Hengstmann	DESY	WP1	0
Franz Hennies	MAX IV Laboratory	WP9	1
Michael Hennig	leadXpro AG		0
Francisco Jose Iguaz Gutierrez	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP2	0
Markus Janousch	Paul Scherrer Institut	WP7	0
Babak Kalantari	Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI)	WP5	0
Axel KAPROLAT	ESRF-ISDD	WP2; WP3; WP5; WP7	1
Klaus Kiefer	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin	WP5	0
Maya Kiskinova	Sincrotrone Trieste	WP9	1
Bastian Klemke		WP5	1

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Ute Krell	DESY	WP1; WP9	0
Magnus Larsson	MAX IV Laboratory	WP8	0
Gael Le Bec	ESRF	WP6	0
Xiaoyang Liang	Paul Scherrer Institut	WP6	0
Beatriz Lorenzo		WP5; WP7; WP8; WP9	0
Krzysztof Madura	NCPS Solaris UJ	WP7	0
Mikako Makita	Eur.XFEL (European XFEL)	WP3	1
Luis Manzanillas Velez	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP2	0
Jordi Marcos Ruzafa	ALBA Synchrotron	WP6	0
OLIVIER MARCOUILLE	SOLEIL Synchrotron	WP5; WP6	0
Philippe MARION	ESRF	WP5	1
Thierry MARTIN	ESRF	WP2	0
Zdenek Matej	MAX IV Laboratory, Lund University	WP7	0
Oscar Matilla		WP2; WP5	0
Ralf-Hendrik Menk	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste	WP2	0
Atoosa Meseck	HZB / JGU	WP6	0
Tom Minniberger	EUP (EU-Projekt)	WP1	0
Ed Mitchell	European Synchrotron	WP8	0
Alberto Mittone	CELLS	WP7	0
Michał Młynarczyk	SOLARIS	WP8	1
Cristina Modolo	Elettra - Sincrotrone Trieste S.C.p.A.	WP8	0
Bernat Molas Pous	ALBA Synchrotron	WP8	1
Søren Møller	ISA, University of Aarhus, Denmark	WP6; WP8	0
Christian Morawe	ESRF	WP3; WP4	1
Stefan Müller	Paul Scherrer Institut	WP8	1
Matthias Neeb	Helmholtz-Zentrum-Berlin, HZB	WP5	0
Federico Nguyen	ENEA	WP6	1
Josep Nicolas	ALBA synchrotron light source	WP3	0
DORIANA ORBANIC	User Office, MAX IV	WP9	1
Fabienne ORSINI	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP2	0
Majid Ounsy	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP7	0
Deike Pahl	European XFEL	WP9	1
ALESSANDRA PATERA	CELLS	WP4; WP7	0
Marco Peloi		WP6; WP8	0
David Pennicard	DESY	WP7	0
Javier Perez	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP5	0
Alberto Petralia	ENEA	WP6	1
Lorenzo Pivetta	Elettra - Sincrotrone Trieste S.C.p.A.	WP7	0

Elke Ploenjes-Palm	DESY	WP3; WP4	0
François POLACK	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP3; WP4	1
Anton Popov	ESRF		1
Matteo Porro	European XFEL GmbH		0
Marcos Quispe	ALBA Synchrotron Light Source	WP2	0
Christoph Quitmann	RI - Research Instruments	WP8	0
Lorenzo Raimondi	Elettra-Sincrotrone Trieste	WP3; WP4	0
Britta Redlich	FELIX, Radboud University	WP8; WP9	0
Ed Rial	HZB	WP6	0
Jean-Paul Ricaud	Synchrotron Soleil	WP5	0
Alison Roblin	Diamond Light Source	WP8	1
Nazanin Samadi	PSI	WP4	0
Alejandro Sanchez Grueso	ALBA Synchrotron	WP8	0
Uwe Sassenberg	ITT (Innovation und Technologietransfer)	WP8	0
Kawal Sawhney	Diamond Light Source	WP3; WP4	1
Thomas Schmidt	Paul Scherrer Institute	WP6	0
Silja Schmidtchen	Eur.XFEL (European XFEL)	WP3	0
Bernd Schmitt		WP2	0
Gerd Schneider	Helmholtz Center Berlin	WP5	1
Frank Scholze	PTB	WP4; WP8	0
Joachim Schulz	Eur.XFEL (European XFEL)	WP5	0
Oliver Seeck	DESY	WP5	0
Xavier Serra-Gallifa	CELLS - ALBA Synchrotron	WP5	0
Elizabeth Shotton	Diamond Light Source	WP8	0
Frank Siewert	Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin	WP3; WP4	0
Egor Sobolev	Eur.XFEL (European XFEL)	WP7	0
Nicolas Soler	ALBA-CELLS	WP7	0
Darren Spruce	MAX IV Laboratory	WP7	0
Hamed Tarawneh	MAX IV Laboratory, Lund University	WP6	0
Marc Thiry	Hereon	WP8	0
Muriel Thomasset	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP3; WP4	1
Heine Thomsen	ISA - Centre for Storage Ring Facilities, Aarhus University	WP6	1
Markus Tischer	FS-US (Undulator Systeme)	WP6	1
Takashi Tomizaki	Paul Scherrer Institut	WP5	1
Soichiro Tsujino	Paul Scherrer Institut	WP5	0
Ana VALCARCEL ORTI	SOLEIL	WP9	0
Mathieu VALLEAU		WP6	0
Nuria Valls	ALBA-CELLS	WP8	0
Maurizio Vannoni	Eur.XFEL (European XFEL)	WP3	0
François Villar	ESRF	WP5	0

Amparo VIVO	ESRF	WP3; WP4	0
Dirk Wallacher	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie	WP5	0
Hongchang Wang	Diamond Light Source	WP3; WP4	0
Adriana Wawrzyniak	SOLARIS	WP6	0
Hans Weise	DESY	external speaker	1
Jaroslav Wiechecki	SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre	WP6	0
Tim Wilksen	DESY	WP5	1
Kinga Wróbel	SOLARIS NSRC	WP8	1
Nikolaj ZANGENBERG	Danish Technological Institute	WP8	1
Shu ZHANG	Synchrotron SOLEIL	WP5; WP7	0
Christiaan Zonnevylle	Raith BV	WP4	0

